

Oral Presentation #47 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Muhammed Emin Goktepe
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9587-4496>

Koray Keskin
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4333-2842>

AFFILIATIONS

Gorele Op. Dr. Ergun Ozdemir State Hospital
Giresun, Turkey

Kanuni Research and Training Hospital
Trabzon, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The genioglossus and geniohyoid muscles are situated medially to the sublingual cavity, but the mylohyoid muscle is located inferolaterally to it. The mylohyoid muscle is a crucial element forming the floor of the mouth. The mylohyoid muscle acts as a muscular partition between the sublingual and submandibular areas.

Case Presentation: A 25-year-old female patient appeared with a bulge behind the left jaw, which she had observed for approximately one year. The woman was initially brought to our clinic due to concerns over potential malignancy in her neck. During the physical examination, a non-mobile, approximately 2 cm diameter, smooth-surfaced mass lesion is observed in the submandibular region that is elicited by swallowing. Ultrasonographic examination revealed a 22x12 mm soft tissue in the submandibular region. As a preliminary diagnosis, mass in the submandibular gland tissue, herniation in the submandibular gland and surrounding soft tissues, lipoma and congenital cyst were considered. Magnetic resonance imaging was recommended for further investigation. Neutral magnetic resonance imaging showed a fascia defect in the left anterior part, provoked swallowing or valsalva maneuver was performed, mylohyoid muscle herniation was detected. No mass image was seen.

Conclusion: SLG (sublingual) herniation is a common condition. In a cadaveric study conducted in Korea, the incidence of herniations was similar to that reported in European studies. Out of 100 SLGs, 42 herniated and were more common in women. It has been reported that one or a combination of fat, muscle tissue or salivary gland tissue may herniate from these defects at variable rates. In our case, the clinical presentation was asymptomatic except for the presence of an immobile and cosmetically uncomfortable mass in the neck that appeared with swallowing. It should be kept in mind among the differential diagnoses in patients evaluated with a mass in the submandibular region of the neck. Failure to clearly identify the mylohyoid muscle defect on radiologic imaging may cause unnecessary anxiety and unnecessary prediagnoses such as malignancy.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Mylohyoid muscle, herniation, submandibular gland

INTRODUCTION

The genioglossus and geniohyoid muscles are situated medially to the sublingual cavity, but the mylohyoid muscle is located inferolaterally to it. The mylohyoid muscle is a crucial element forming the floor of the mouth. The mylohyoid muscle acts as a muscular partition between the sublingual and submandibular areas. (Rosen & Bailey, 2001) However, abnormalities in the mylohyoid muscle and soft tissue herniations frequently encountered in cadaver dissections and CT (computerized tomography) scans pose a diagnostic problem (Engel et al., 1987; White et al., 2001; Yang et al., 2016).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A 25-year-old female patient appeared with a bulge behind the left jaw, which she had observed for approximately one year. The woman was initially brought to our clinic due to concerns over potential malignancy in her neck. During the physical examination, a non-mobile, approximately 2 cm diameter, smooth-surfaced mass lesion is observed in the submandibular region that is elicited by swallowing (Figure 1).

Figure 1

The patient has no prior medical history. Her sole surgical history consists of a rhinoplasty performed two years ago. Other than that, she had no additional disease and did not use any medication. Ultrasonographic examination revealed a 22x12 mm soft tissue in the submandibular region. As a preliminary diagnosis, mass in the submandibular gland tissue, herniation in the submandibular gland and surrounding soft tissues, lipoma and congenital cyst were considered. Magnetic resonance imaging was recommended for further investigation. Neutral magnetic resonance imaging showed a fascia defect in the left anterior part, provoked swallowing or valsalva maneuver was performed, mylohyoid muscle herniation was detected. No mass image was seen (Figure 2).

Figure 2

This study does not require ethics committee approval. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

RESULTS

SLG (sublingual) herniation is a common condition. In a cadaveric study conducted in Europe, mylohyoid herniation was detected in 45 of 100 adult cadavers. (Engel, J. D., Harn, S. D., & Cohen, D. M. (1987). In a cadaveric study conducted in Korea, the incidence of herniations was similar to that reported in European studies. Out of 100 SLGs, 42 herniated and were more common in women. Similar to our case, 63% of total herniations were reported in the anterior part of the mylohyoid muscle. In another a cadaveric study of 50 cases, degenerative changes were observed in the herniated part of the sublingual gland (Kim, H. C., Yang, H. C., Cho, H. J., & Nam, K. I. (2019). In another clinical study, 77 out of 100 people who underwent CT scanning showed defects in the mylohyoid muscle. It has been reported that one or a combination of fat, muscle tissue or salivary gland tissue may herniate from these defects at variable rates. In 61% of these cases, herniation of the salivary gland was observed in 61% fat, 42% vascular structures and 37% salivary gland (White, D. K., Davidson, H. C., Harnsberger, H. R., Haller, J., & Kamyra, A. (2001).

DISCUSSION

In our case, the clinical presentation was asymptomatic except for the presence of an immobile and cosmetically uncomfortable mass in the neck that appeared with swallowing. The clinical presentation may vary depending on the size of the herniation, the size of the defect in the mylohyoid muscle and the amount of herniated gland or soft tissues. Although mylohyoid muscle defects and soft tissue herniations are common, they are generally asymptomatic and are mostly diagnosed in screening studies and cadaver dissections. And for this reason, it poses a diagnostic difficulty.

CONCLUSION

It should be kept in mind among the differential diagnoses in patients evaluated with a mass in the submandibular region of the neck. Failure to clearly identify the mylohyoid muscle defect on radiologic imaging may cause unnecessary anxiety and unnecessary prediagnoses such as malignancy (Sher, Z. A., & Tan, G. (2016).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Engel, J. D., Harn, S. D., & Cohen, D. M. (1987). Mylohyoid herniation: Gross and histologic evaluation with clinical correlation. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology*, 63(1), 55–59. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-4220\(87\)90340-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-4220(87)90340-9)
- Kim, H. C., Yang, H. C., Cho, H. J., & Nam, K. I. (2019). Histologic features of sublingual gland herniation through the mylohyoid muscle. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Pathology*, 12(12), 4303–4308.
- Rosen, F. S., & Bailey, B. J. (2001). *Anatomy and physiology of the salivary glands* (5th ed.). UTMB.
- Sher, Z. A., & Tan, G. (2016). Unilateral sublingual salivary gland hypertrophy with herniation through a boutonnière defect and contralateral sublingual gland hypoplasia. *BJR Case Reports*, 2(3), 20150382. <https://doi.org/10.1259/bjrcr.20150382>
- White, D. K., Davidson, H. C., Harnsberger, H. R., Haller, J., & Kamyra, A. (2001). Accessory salivary tissue in the mylohyoid boutonnière: A clinical and radiologic pseudolesion of the oral cavity. *AJNR. American Journal of Neuroradiology*, 22(2), 406–412.
- Yang, H. C., Kim, S. Y., Kim, S. K., Oh, C. S., Chung, I. H., & Nam, K. I. (2016). A cadaveric study on mylohyoid herniation of the sublingual gland. *European Archives of Oto-Rhino-Laryngology*, 273, 4413–4416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00405-016-4095-1>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Muhammed Emin Goktepe

Gorele Op. Dr. Ergun Ozdemir State Hospital

Giresun, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9587-4496>

drmeg38@gmail.com